

Strategy for Establishing Environmental Communication in Instilling Environmental Care Behavior at Adiwiyata School, Bekasi 7 Sma Negeri

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Abstract:- School as an educational unit that is capable of optimizing all environmental learning to build, strengthen, or continuously improve educational character processes, including the character of caring for the environment as a form of the adiwiyata program at SMA Negeri 7 Bekasi. Adiwiyata Program, developed based on norms in life which include: togetherness, openness, equality, honesty, fairness and preservation of environmental functions and natural resources. The goal is to create good conditions for schools to become places of learning and to raise awareness among school members to take responsibility for efforts to save the environment and sustainable development. The principles of Adiwiyata are Educative, Participatory and Sustainable. The purpose of this study was to find out the strategy for establishing environmental communication carried out by the Civitas SMA Negeri 7 Bekasi in instilling Environmental Care Behavior to all students at this Adiwiyata School. By using the concept of environmental communication which is linked to the Sustainable Development Goals in an effort to instill Environmentally Concerned Behavior among students. As well as using the theory used is the Theory of Planned Behavior from Fishbein and Ajzen.

The research results and conclusions obtained are as follows: (1) The environmental communication strategy implemented by SMAN 7 Bekasi is monolithic, depending on a leader, namely the Principal with a commitment and heart to maintain cleanliness and greenery in the school environment. (2) The Environmental Communication Strategy is also carried out by placing concern for the environment in the School Mission and the School's Motto, "Be Passionate" (3) SMAN 7 Bekasi applies the Adiwiyata Principles in instilling Environmentally Concerned Behavior. These principles are: a. Educative, b. Participatory, and c. Continuity. (4) SMAN 7 Bekasi has consistently implemented the Caring for the environment activity which covers the following aspects: a. Environmental Aspects of School Policy b. Aspects of the School Curriculum that are based on the environment, c. Aspects of Management of Environmentally Friendly School Support Facilities and Infrastructure, d. Aspects of participatory-based environmental activities in schools, (5) Environmental care behavior instilled in students includes: a. Energy Saving, b. Mobility and Transportation, c. Waste prevention, d. Waste

management and waste recycling, e. Wise use of water, f. Participation in environmental maintenance.

Keywords:- Strategy, Formation of Environmental Communication, Adiwiyata School, Environmental Care Behavior, Theory of Planned Behavior.

I. INTRODUCTION

The environmental problems currently faced by humans are floods, natural disasters, landslides, waste problems, water and air pollution and pollution as well as climate change issues. What is faced by humans in relation to nature, is closely related to human behavior itself in managing nature and the environment. The behavior of littering, irresponsible cutting of forests, and the narrowing of green land planted with trees for water catchment areas, often results in problems such as water shortages during droughts. Human awareness to plant trees is decreasing. Especially in urban areas, many people's houses do not leave empty land for planting trees, and household waste has piled up mainly dominated by plastic waste.

Not only that, the above environmental problems are not new, but are the same as the age of our earth, which according to experts, is around 5 (five) billion years old. The proof is that thousands of species of animals and plants have become extinct. According to Soemartowo in Aziz (2013: 1), their extinction may not come suddenly without being related to the ecosystem. Erwati in Aziz (2013: 7) explains that in developing countries environmental problems are no less important than in developed countries, but the cases and causes are not the same. If in developed countries the main cause is industrial waste such as mercury, toxic gases, smog etc., then in developing countries like Indonesia it is household waste and human waste.

The main environmental problem is being able to make people aware that they no longer take actions that cause a decrease in the quality of the environment, and with full awareness they stop doing those actions, then turn around to carry out activities that can preserve the environment so that the ecosystem is safe and its sustainability is maintained. There are many ways that can be done to provide a good understanding of the environment for each individual, such as information, counseling, guidance, and education (formal and non-formal starting from kindergarten, elementary school to university) (Yafie, 2009: 50).

Seeing the various environmental problems that occur in Indonesia, the government expects that the responsibility will not be placed solely on the government, but also be a joint responsibility of all elements of society. What can be done is not only trying to take action to save and respond to disasters caused by nature and the environment but requires collective and participatory awareness from all elements of society to jointly protect the environment. Caring behavior and environmentally friendly attitude is a must that can not be avoided anymore. And caring behavior and an environmentally friendly attitude do not materialize by themselves. But it requires knowledge, coaching and nurturing.

Environmental issues are one of the pillars of sustainable development called the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) whose ideas emerged at the United Nations Summit in New York in 2015. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are a global action plan agreed upon by world leaders, including Indonesia, to end poverty, reduce inequality and protect the environment. The SDGs contain 17 Goals and 169 Targets that are expected to be achieved by 2030 (<http://www.sdg2030indonesia.org>, nd).

When the community is patterned with the empowerment process and environmental communication, the next effort is to instill the SDGs goal values. Environmental issues and the importance of environmental preservation need to be conveyed to the community in a planned manner. There is the realizing that is built by the society has to be gone up mainly rising the pattern capacity of communication on giving the communication and campaigning the life pattern of healthy from the rubbish of the house (Subiakto, 2020: 56). Environmental communication activities in disseminating SDGs require competent communicators. Also important to note is the method used in conveying socialization that is easily accepted by the audience who wants to be educated. Socialization activities are carried out in seminars or talk shows that are persuasive, entertaining and motivating. Various environmental communication activities can also be disseminated through the mass media using various self-made publications such as banners, billboards about the environment or through media coverage that conveys news related to various environmental problems, environmental damage and environmental improvement efforts as well as other aspects.

Environmental Education as explained in REGULATION OF THE MINISTER OF ENVIRONMENT AND FORESTRY OF THE REPUBLIC OF INDONESIA NUMBER P.52/MENLHK/SETJEN/KUM.1/9/2019 CONCERNING CARE AND ENVIRONMENTAL CULTURE MOVEMENT IN SCHOOLS is an effort to increase knowledge, skills, attitudes, and the action of individual, community, organization and various parties concerned about environmental issues for sustainable development for present and future generations. With this Perpu, the Ministry of Environment and Forestry hopes that environmental education can be carried out in schools starting from the PAUD level to tertiary institutions.

The school community is expected to play an active role in the Environmental Care and Culture Movement in Schools, hereinafter referred to as the PBLHS Movement, which is a conscious, voluntary, networked and sustainable collective action carried out by schools in implementing environmentally friendly behavior. This PLHBS movement can be carried out by implementing Environmentally Friendly Behavior (abbreviated PRLH) which is the attitude and actions of school members in maintaining and preserving environmental functions. Educational institutions such as schools are expected to be able to identify Environmental Potentials and Problems (hereinafter abbreviated as IPMLH).

Schools as a place to gain knowledge make it possible for its citizens to carry out new innovations for the development of science and knowledge, and schools are also required to provide innovative ideas in their role as educational institutions that care about the environment. Adiwiyata Program, developed based on norms in life which include: togetherness, openness, equality, honesty, fairness and preservation of environmental functions and natural resources. The goal is to create good conditions for schools to become places of learning and to raise awareness among school members to take responsibility for efforts to save the environment and sustainable development.

Integrating environmental culture in students can be trained through various activities. Among other things, environmental education in the curriculum and learning, character building care for the environment, provision of environmental material regarding land conservation, protection of natural resources, local wisdom protecting nature and biodiversity. environmentally friendly. Therefore, the teacher is obliged to provide good knowledge and habituation about the environment to each student. So that schools must be able to maintain and maintain caring behavior towards the environment. Environmental care behavior or better known as environmental care is a behavior or action that always tries to prevent damage to the surrounding natural environment and develops efforts to repair the natural damage that has occurred.

II. THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOR

This theory was developed by Fishbein and Ajzen and is an extension of Theory of Reasoned Action, which aims to predict behavior from attitudes and to explain which processes are interrelated. Both theories of planned behavior and theories of reasoned action focus on the importance of intention to perform certain behaviors. The addition of variables related to perceived control over behavior, also called perceived behavioral control, served to extend the theory of reasoned action into the theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1991). Based on this theory, behavioral intention determines a person's pro-environmental behavior. In TPB theory, there are three variables that determine behavioral intentions, namely attitudes toward behavior, subjective norms, and perceptions of behavioral control (Sawitri, 2017).

The theory of reasoned action assumes that almost all behavior is under the control of a person's progress to perform certain actions. But in reality there are still many behaviors that are not in the person's full control. Some behaviors that experience deficiencies such as those related to skills, abilities, knowledge and good planning. In other behaviors, there may be external obstacles such as time or opportunity that may limit achieving goals, so to accommodate these inhibiting factors, the model from Theory of Reasoned Action becomes Theory of Planned

Behavior. Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), was developed in 1967, then the theory was continuously revised and expanded by Icek Ajzen and Martin Fishbein. In 1980, the theory was used to study human behavior and to develop more appropriate interventions. In 1988, another thing was added behavioral control to the existing reasoned action model, then it was named Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB). (Bursan, January 2010) of planned behavior can be described as follows:

Fig. 1: Theory of planned behavior theory

Source : Burslari, Januari 2010

III. THE CONCEPT OF ENVIRONMENTAL

Communication Environmental communication according to Robert Cox entitled Environment Communication and Public Sphere in 2010, as quoted by Yenrizal in his book entitled Preserving the Earth with Environmental Communication (2017) (Yenrizal, 2017, p. 9) is a pragmatic and constructive medium for educate the public about the environment. Environmental communication concerns strategies for packaging messages in various mediums to raise public awareness and participation in environmental management. Basically environmental communication aims to raise awareness and community participation in managing the environment including forests, the pattern is dialogic, intensive and occurs more in interpersonal communication and group communication, not just providing and disseminating environmental information.

Meanwhile, according to Alexander G. Flor and Hafied Cangara (Cangara, 2018, p. 3), environmental communication is defined as the use of approaches, principles, strategies and communication techniques for environmental management and protection. In the environmental program agenda, communication should not only be seen as an instrument or tool to support the implementation of environmental management, but rather as an integral part of environmental management itself. Through environmental communication, it is expected to raise awareness of the environment from the whole community. Environmental awareness becomes a form of attitude and behavior of tolerance towards the environment.

According to Neoloka (2008), (Elfiandri, 2018, pp. 62-64) the factors that affect the community environment are **First**, the factor of ignorance. **Second**, the poverty factor. Poverty is one of the problems that cause social problems.

Social problems are a condition that is incarnated where people feel that there is a threat that involves many people, social problems stem from poverty or difficulties in meeting basic needs and are often interrelated with other factors such as poor management of natural resources and population explosion. **Third**, the human factor, that humans have basic needs, certain desires, namely physical needs and social needs.

Fourth, lifestyle factors. There are several lifestyles that exacerbate environmental damage, namely (a), a lifestyle that emphasizes enjoyment, partying and debauchery (hedonism), (b) a lifestyle that emphasizes materialism (materialism) and (c) a consumptive lifestyle, (d) a lifestyle a secular life that prioritizes worldliness and (e) a lifestyle that is selfish (individualism).

In order for environmental communication to work effectively, a good communication strategy is needed. This is done considering that environmental communication is not an easy thing to implement, it requires the involvement of many parties. The program created must be well planned, clear, targeted, and involve collaboration and active participation of stakeholders (Kadarisman, 2019, p. 7).

IV. ENVIRONMENTAL COMMUNICATION STRATEGY COMMUNICATION

Strategy which is a combination of communication planning and communication management to achieve the stated goals. The communication strategy must be able to show how operationally it must be carried out practically, in the sense that the approach can differ from time to time depending on the situation and conditions. The success or failure of effective communication activities is largely determined by the communication strategy, strategy is essentially planning and management to achieve a goal. However, to achieve this goal, the strategy does not function

as a road map that only shows direction, but must be able to show how the tactics are operational (Oepen, Environmental Communication for Sustainable Development, 1999, p. 5).

Environmental communication itself is a plan and strategy through communication processes and media products to support the effectiveness of policy making, public participation, and its implementation in the environment. Manfred Oepen and Winfred Hamacher (Oepen, Environmental Communication for Sustainable Development, 1999, p. 6) suggested that the steps for establishing an environmental communication strategy consisted of 10 steps, namely:

Stage 1 Assessment, namely situation analysis and problem identification, analysis of the parties or actors involved and communication objective (to increase knowledge, influence behavior). Stage 2 Planning, namely developing a communication strategy, motivating and mobilizing the community, and choosing media. Stage 3 Message Production, namely the design of the message to be conveyed, media production accompanied by a pretest. Stage 4 Action and Reflection, namely Dissemination through the media and its implementation and Documentation, monitoring and evaluation processes.

V. SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS (SDGS)

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) or Sustainable Development Goals (TPB) is a term that describes a global development program that is targeted to end in 2030. The development goals in the SDGs program consist of 17 points, namely: No Poverty, No Hunger, Health, Education, Gender Equality, Sanitation and Access to Clean Water, Clean and Affordable Energy, Economy and Decent Work, Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure, Reducing Inequalities, Sustainable Cities and Communities, Responsible Consumption and Production, Climate Change Action, Ecosystems Water, Land Ecosystems, Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions, and Partnerships to Achieve Goals.

The principles for implementing the SDGs, as quoted from the <https://www.icctf.or.id/sdgs/> page, are: a) Universal: implemented by the whole world in relation to goals and objectives that are transformative, human-centered, comprehensive, and long term b) Integration: implemented in an integrated manner in all social, economic and environmental dimensions (interrelated) c) No-One Left Behind: Implemented by involving all stakeholders and providing benefits for all, especially the vulnerable. The SDGs are committed to sustainable development that is based on integrated social, economic and environmental aspects, which are expected to create global prosperity. In essence, sustainable development is to ensure that future generations can enjoy their daily needs like the current generation (Kadarisman, Environmental Communication: Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) Approach and Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), 2019, pp. 23-25).

VI. RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a qualitative research approach with a descriptive type. The qualitative approach sees social reality as something that is whole (holistic), complex, dynamic and full of meaning. Researchers seek to see phenomena naturally (natural settings) where researchers are key instruments, data collection techniques are carried out in a triangulation (combined) manner in order to obtain in-depth data and emphasize more on the meaning of the phenomenon under study rather than generalization (Sugiono, 2007: 1-3). The nature of the research to be taken is descriptive. This type of descriptive research was chosen by the researcher because the researcher wanted to describe how the implementation of the environmental care movement is an effort to increase public awareness of protecting the environment in the Jatisampurna sub-district. Through analysis of this environmental care movement, it is hoped that researchers can describe and reveal how the implementation of environmental care activities can increase public awareness in keeping the environment clean in the Jatisampurna sub-district area. Thus this study will describe the various results and findings in a narrative and descriptive manner. The subjects of this study included: Mrs. Tri Sumarti, Spd, as Deputy Head of School for the Environment for the 2006-2014 period, Mr. Edy Sunarya, Spd, M,pd as Public Relations of SMAN 7 Bekasi., Mr. Mujiono S.Pd, as Extracurricular Guidance Teacher Environment., Head of Extracurricular Environment. As well as students of SMAN 7 Bekasi. To determine the validity of the data, the researchers carried out a triangulation technique. Triangulation is a data checking technique that utilizes something other than research data for checking purposes or as a comparison. Denzin distinguishes four kinds of triangulation as an examination technique that utilizes the use of sources, methods, investigators and theories (Moleong, 2013, p. 330).

VII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

• Strategies for Establishing Environmental Communication in Instilling Environmentally Concerned Behavior at the Adiwiyata School SMA Negeri 7 Bekasi

Environmental communication as described by Robert Cox as a pragmatic and constructive medium to provide understanding and awareness about the environment. In carrying out the strategy of forming environmental communication in instilling Caring for the Environment behavior at the Adiwiyata School, SMA Negeri 7 Bekasi, several functions are needed to carry out this role. one of which is to carry out a pragmatic educational function in terms of solving environmental problems. Then carry out, a constitutive function that will assist in understanding environmental problems and natural representations that can form knowledge about nature.

Carrying out environmental communication is not an easy thing, therefore, it is necessary to have a strategy carried out in the formation of this communication in instilling environmentally caring behavior towards the younger generation, especially for SMA Negeri 7 Bekasi students. Things that can be done in implementing a strategy for forming environmental communication by packaging messages are carried out in various media to raise awareness and community participation in environmental management. This awareness and participation needs to be carried out by the younger generation, especially students of SMA Negeri 7 Bekasi to create an Adiwiyata school. Where awareness is made to try to eradicate and educate environmental problems.

The strategy for establishing environmental communication needs to be done with a communication pattern that is dialogical, intensive and occurs more frequently in interpersonal communication and group communication. Environmental Communication Strategy as the first step in carrying out the process of environmental communication as a form of education or literacy for the younger generation, especially for SMA Negeri 7 Bekasi students. Not only that, in the formation of communication it is necessary to have a strategy to consider as supporting and inhibiting factors in the steps for forming environmental communication to students with changes in Environmental Care behavior.

The stages in carrying out an environmental communication strategy in instilling environmental care behavior for SMA Negeri 7 Bekasi students include:

VIII. ASSESSMENT STAGE

At this stage, analyze the situation and identify the problem as well as analyze who is involved in it and the objectives of environmental communication to be achieved. Where in this stage, the formation of communication was carried out by the Principal of SMA Negeri 7 Bekasi for the period 2005-2007 who played a role in instilling awareness and love for the environment and implementing go green in the school environment. The school principal becomes a driving force for all school members involved in environmental care activities.

Principal of SMAN 7 Bekasi, really loves the environment or cares about the environment. Implementation in structuring the school environment is carried out with a high commitment so that the school becomes a comfortable, safe and green place for all school members. The area of the school which reaches 5000 meters can be planted with trees and other plants so that the school environment is not arid. The main focus of this school is maintaining the environment by carrying out tree planting activities and cleaning activities in the school environment. The goal to be achieved from planting trees and cleaning the school environment is to create a comfortable, safe and green learning environment. This program is the commitment and seriousness of the school in managing the school environment. Not only that, the involvement of the Vice Principal for School Environment SMAN 7 Bekasi in

providing a green and clean school environment arrangement can be fully implemented if there is someone who is focused on carrying out this task.

The involvement of the Deputy Principal in the Environment field has made environmental activities increasingly receiving serious attention not only at the internal school level but also starting to participate in various environmental activities outside of school. Starting in 2005, the school took part in cleanliness and greening competitions between schools at the sub-district level until SMAN 7 Bekasi won an award as an Environmental Culture School at the Bekasi City level. Then, in 2006, SMAN 7 Bekasi was included in the Adiwiyata School Program representing the City of Bekasi. Adiwiyata School is developed based on norms in life which include: togetherness, openness, equality, honesty, fairness and the preservation of environmental functions and natural resources. The aim is to create good conditions for schools to become places of learning and awareness of school members to take responsibility for efforts to save the environment and sustainable development. Therefore, objective communication is needed to increase knowledge and influence the behavior of school members about the Adiwiyata Program.

IX. ASSESSMENT STAGE

The initial step for SMAN 7 Kota Bekasi in participating in the Adiwiyata program was to add environmental awareness to the mission statement of SMAN 7 Kota Bekasi, namely "Growing a spirit of caring in maintaining the school environment." Furthermore, the mission is implemented into the school's motto, which is known as the word "EXCITED" which is clean, healthy, independent, fun, safe and orderly. The words clean and healthy are the top two mottos that want to be conveyed to all stakeholders inside and outside the school. Furthermore, schools began to apply Adiwiyata principles consisting of:

A. *Educative Principles.*

This principle emphasizes environmental education carried out by schools through various kinds of habituation, such as how to educate all school members to carry out maintenance, preservation and management of the environment to change the mindset and behavior of school members to become human beings who care about the environment, to make citizens who aspire to a good environment. at school, at home and in the community.

The educational principle is poured into school policies that are environmentally sound. This aspect is implemented through various policies such as: School Policy in developing environmental education. Policies for increasing Human Resources (HR) for both educators and education staff in the field of Environmental Education. School Policies in terms of Saving Water Resources. School Policies that support the creation of a clean and healthy school environment. School policies for allocating and using funds for activities related to the environment.

The environmental education policy is implemented in an environment-based school curriculum in the form of: First, developing a cross-subject learning model. Caring for the environment activities are carried out in a monolithic manner which is defined as activities outside of the teaching and learning process but integrated into the school curriculum. The cultivation of environmental care behavior is included in the school curriculum. With integration into the school curriculum, efforts to identify environmental issues and their application are included in each existing subject in the form of both individual and group assignments.

For example, art teachers assign poster competitions and create songs with environmental themes. The winner will receive a prize and his work will be installed in main rooms such as the principal's room, teacher's room, administration room. Apart from that, they also put up posters in each class. Next, the Biology teacher assigns students to bring trees, plant trees and record the Latin names of the trees they carry. Tree planting is done in the front yard of each class. The Indonesian teacher assigned her students to write essays about the environment, and one of the essays made by students was included in an essay competition organized by Kompas Daily and won.

Second, the development of learning methods based on environment and culture. Environmental and culture-based learning methods are applied by teaching students to recognize their surroundings and making caring for the environment a school culture that guides behavior while at school. The inculcation of discipline in disposing of waste in its place is accompanied by sanctions for those who violate it. The first sanction, students are asked to make a statement of regret for the behavior of littering. The next sanction is the punishment for cleaning the classroom or school yard. Until the final sanction in the form of money. The first sanction is able to provide a deterrent effect for students so that it does not continue with the second and third sanctions.

Third, exploration and development of existing environmental materials and issues through environmental subjects. Lessons about the environment are included in the curriculum. Fourth, Development of extra-curricular activities to increase students' knowledge and awareness about the environment. Students form an Extracurricular Environment (ELH) fostered by the vice principal of the environmental field. With ELH, students are taught and instilled awareness to care about nature conservation and maintain a clean and healthy environment through various school greening and cleaning activities, learning to grow hydroponic plants, cultivating fish, and learning to process waste into compost which is then sold to the community. around. This activity went well before the pandemic. And during the pandemic, the Joint Large-Scale Restrictions (PSBB) policy which closed schools, various environmental activities temporarily stopped.

Water is an important natural resource for people's lives. Limited water sources must be used wisely by all school members. The school always reminds its school residents to save water use by using enough water and

closing it again. Saving natural resources is also carried out on electrical energy sources. Students are taught to turn off the electricity when the classroom is no longer in use. Posters warning to save water and electricity are displayed clearly and at the ceremony, students are always advised to save water and electricity. . Students are asked to remind each other.

The school's policy for allocating and using funds for environmental care activities is fully supported by the school. There is a special budget of 20% of the school's operational funds allocated for environmental care activities. Then, there is the participation of the school committee, namely a collection of parents of students in the form of regular donations given every month. Funds are also obtained from activities carried out by the school such as organizing bazaars, selling compost production and often receiving financial support from individual parents of students. So the issue of funding is not a problem. However, they have never received funding from outside parties in the form of partnerships between schools and corporate partners, the government or non-profit organizations. They don't know how to get access to partnerships so they really hope for assistance in building partnership partnerships with sponsors. Here, the role of higher education institutions can be a mediator or intermediary for the school and sponsor partners.

Furthermore, the management aspect of environmentally friendly school facilities and supporting infrastructure is one of the assessments of the adiwiyata program. The existence of infiltration wells built by the school makes the water channels not flow outside the school but seep into the ground. Water infiltration into the ground makes the availability of groundwater sufficient for school needs. With a large yard, the land that becomes water absorption is very useful for the environment. Biopori holes are made in every existing water channel. The arrangement of environmental suggestions was also divided based on themes from extracurriculars in SMAN 7 Kota Bekasi. There is a volleyball court area, basketball for volleyball and basketball extracurriculars, hydroponic and fish farming areas for environmental extracurriculars, as well as other areas that are compatible with other extracurriculars. There are art areas, cultural areas, literacy areas and so on.

Education is also carried out for students, especially students who are members of ELH, who are taught how to manage waste with the 3R principles, namely reduce, reuse, recycle. The first step, students are taught to separate organic and an organic waste. The principle of reduce, students and all school residents are asked to bring their own drink tumbler and food supplies from home. That way, the use of plastic and plastic waste will decrease. Waste management is separated between organic and an organic. Students are asked to be disciplined in disposing of garbage according to the type of waste. Those who violate will be subject to sanctions. Then, the organic waste is recycled into compost. The processed compost is marketed to the surrounding community. Plastic waste is converted into crafts that are taught in skills subjects.

Environmental extracurriculars have an Instagram social media channel, namely @elhsman7bekasi. Instagram media is a medium of information and communication of their activities. The ELH management manages social media channels under the guidance of Extra Environmental Guidance Teachers. During Mrs. Tri Sumarti's tenure as Deputy Deputy for Environment, the Instagram social media channel was active. He served from 2006-2014 until the leadership of Principal Mrs. Ida Farida. After releasing this position, until now there is no one assigned to hold this special position. Thus, the activity of instilling environmental care behavior as an aspect of sustainability is not going well. In addition, since March 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic hit Indonesia so that the government implemented large-scale restrictions, schools and colleges were closed. Environmental activities are carried out from home by ELH students with directions from the guidance teacher via Zoom or Google Meet.

B. Participative

Principle This principle implies that the implementation of the Adiwiyata Program must be carried out in a comprehensive manner, starting from the government to the community, through planning, implementation and evaluation that involves the community. Likewise, participatory activities carried out at schools also involve parents and the surrounding community in collaborating in carrying out environmental care activities. The participatory form carried out by SMAN 7 Bekasi City is manifested in the participation of various activities related to moments or celebrations of environmental holidays. In the participative principle carrying out activities including community service activities, greening and environmental management are carried out together with all school members, namely the school principal and his leadership, teachers, parents of students who are members of the school committee and staff and students.

This activity was routinely carried out every month before the pandemic hit. During the pandemic, this activity was halted and resumed on February 21 2021 as an effort to prepare schools to welcome 100% face-to-face learning activities in the new 2021-2022 academic year in July 2021. There is a strong will in carrying out greenery and environmental management that has made this school maintain the attitude and behavior of Adiwiyata school residents. Achievement as an Adiwiyata School is difficult to maintain if it does not have the support of all school members.

In motivating and mobilizing school members, the school principal and vice principal for the environmental sector have a big role. They become the driving force for all school members to participate in protecting and preserving the environment around the school. Participatory form carried out by all school members, including the school committee. Weekly community service activities are carried out by students to clean up their respective classes. Cleaning and greening activities are also carried out together with the environment around the school such as RT, RW, Kelurahan and Kecamatan. Through community service, SMAN 7 Bekasi City builds good cooperation with the community in

shaping environmental care behavior. SMAN 7 Bekasi City is a role model for other schools and the surrounding community in the Jatisampurna District area.

C. The Principle of Sustainability

The principle of Sustainability implies that this Adiwiyata Program is planned, continuous and sustainable. With the vice principal for the environmental sector formed by the Deputy Principal for the Environment Sector, the sustainability of environmental management continues under the coordination of the Deputy Principal for the Environment Sector. The role of the Deputy Principal for the Environment Sector is very large in encouraging the creation of environmentally caring behavior. Sustainability in instilling environmental care behavior makes the principal's initial commitment to maintaining the sustainability of instilling environmental care behavior a consequence of becoming an Adiwiyata School. This program is carried out when the Principal of the School is in office for a period of 2-4 years, so his leadership can carry out and accommodate environmental care activities very much depending on the intention and will of the next leader.

However, the current problem is that concern for caring for the environment in schools is stagnant due to lack of support from school principals. After the absence of a vice principal who handled the special environmental field, it was considered to be a factor in hampering various environmental activities at this school. Young teachers don't have the courage to carry out this arduous task so that environmental activities at school are mostly carried out by the Environmental Extracurricular. The regeneration process did not run smoothly, it is great hope that the young teachers who become coaches of ELH can revitalize Care for the Environment activities. Ahead of the implementation of 100% face-to-face learning in the new 2021-2022 school year.

The strategy in forming environmental communication in instilling environmental care behavior in the adiwiyata school at SMA Negeri 7 Bekasi is by holding environmental awareness activities to celebrate National Waste Care Day on February 21, 2022. This environmental activity was the first to be carried out during the pandemic. All levels of SMA Negeri 7 Bekasi, both the principal and school committees, carry out greening activities and environmental management. Students have changes in environmental care behavior that are instilled in school residents at SMAN 7 Bekasi City including: Energy Saving, Mobility and transportation, Waste Prevention, Waste Management and waste recycling, Utilization of Water and Electricity, Participation in Environmental maintenance.

Of the six indicators, all of them were successfully instilled in students as well as the entire school community. So that environmental care behavior becomes their daily behavior in the school environment. In the observations of researchers when visiting this school, the expanse of green, clean grass and shady trees in this school, provides an illustration of how the behavior of caring for the environment has been well instilled. The school environment is well organized.

X. MESSAGE PRODUCTION STAGE

In instilling environmental care behavior, there is coordination between the Principal and the Deputy Principal in the environmental field, packaging messages that are tailored to the intended target audience. Messages are conveyed through various existing communication media such as policies, regulations and appeals written on internal media such as posters, pamphlets, leaflets and internal memos. The message production stage was carried out by the school with posters made by students with an environmental theme which contained calls to care for the environment such as disposing of trash in its place, using water and electricity wisely. Not only that, the canteen is also called the "Natural Canteen" where there is a fish pond nearby as a place for cultivation for ELH activities, surrounded by shady trees, the beauty of the "natural canteen" is felt. In the canteen, cleanliness is maintained.

At this school, there is no visible trash scattered about and the students bring their own drinking and food containers and use environmentally friendly items such as plates made of bamboo which are placed on banana leaves. The use of plastic is minimal. In the canteen you can also see various posters and pamphlets urging them to maintain cleanliness.

XI. EVALUATION

Phase This Evaluation Phase was carried out by the Bekasi 7 Public High School for the activities carried out for the formation of communication in instilling environmental care behavior at the Adiwiyata School of Bekasi 7 Public High School. As an Adiwiyata school, there is an obligation to report the results of an annual evaluation of the sustainability of Caring for the Environment activities. The evaluation relates to the following matters:

- Environmentally Friendly Policy, has standards;
 - Education Unit Level Curriculum (KTSP) includes efforts to protect and manage the environment.
 - RKAS contains programs in efforts to protect and manage the environment.
- Implementation of Environment-Based Curriculum, has standards;
 - Educators have competence in developing environmental learning activities.
 - Students carry out learning activities about environmental protection and management.
- Participatory Based Environmental Activities have standards;
 - Carry out planned environmental protection and management activities for school residents.
 - Establish partnerships in the framework of environmental protection and management with various parties (community, government, private sector, media, other schools).
- Management of Environmentally Friendly Support Facilities has standards;
 - Availability of environmentally friendly supporting infrastructure.

- Improving the quality of management of environmentally friendly facilities and infrastructure in schools.

This report has been routinely carried out by SMAN 7 Bekasi since it was named the Adiwiyata School in 2019. This annual report is stored neatly in the school library.

XII. CONCLUSION

There are at least five strategies implemented by SMA NEGERI 7 BEKASI in establishing environmental communication in order to instill caring behavior for the environment as an adiwiyata school, including:

- The environmental communication strategy implemented by SMAN 7 Bekasi is monolithic, depending on a leader, namely the Principal with a commitment and heart to maintain cleanliness and greenery in the school environment.
- The Environmental Communication Strategy is also carried out by placing concern for the environment in the School Mission, namely point 4 which explains efforts to foster a caring spirit in maintaining the school environment. And also in the School Motto, Clean and healthy are the first and second points in the School Motto which are known as the word "EXCITED"
- As an adiwiyata school, SMAN 7 Bekasi applies the Adiwiyata Principles in instilling Environmentally Concerned Behavior. These principles are: Educative, Participatory and Sustainability.
- The strategy for forming environmental communication in instilling environmental care behavior at SMA NEGERI 7 BEKASI school as an ADIWIYATA school through consistent Caring for the environment activities until now which includes the following aspects: Aspects of School Policy with an Environmental Insight, Aspects of the School Curriculum based on the environment, Aspects of Management of Environmentally Friendly School Support Facilities and Infrastructure, Aspects of participatory-based environmental activities in schools.
- Environmental care behavior at SMA NEGERI 7 BEKASI school as an ADIWIYATA school that is instilled in students includes: Energy Saving, Mobility and Transportation, Waste Prevention, Waste Management and Waste Recycling, Wise Utilization of Water. Participation in environmental maintenance

REFERENCES

- [1.] Anna, L. K. (2012, Maret 30). *SMA 7 Bekasi, Sekolah Berwawasan Lingkungan*. <https://edukasi.kompas.com/read/2012/03/30/10074259/sma-7-bekasi-sekolah-berwawasan-lingkungan?page=all>
- [2.] Arief Purnama, S. (2018, Maret 23). *Kompasiana.com*. <https://www.kompasiana.com/ariefpurnama/5ab4ddc516835f3ab713a6e2/program-adiwiyata-mewujudkan-sekolah-peduli-lingkungan>
- [3.] Basrowi. (2008). *Memahami Penelitian Kualitatif*. Jakarta: PT RIneka Cipta.

- [4.] Bursan, R. (Januari 2010). Implementation of Planned Behavior Theory at the Faculty of Economics . *Jurnal Bisnis dan Manajemen Volume 6 No.2*.
- [5.] Cangara, A. G. (2018). *Komunikasi Lingkungan: Penanganan Kasus-kasus Lingkungan Melalui Strategi Komunikasi*. Jakarta: Prenada Media Grup.
- [6.] Danandjaja. (2011). *Peranan Humas Dalam Perusahaan*. Bandung: Graha Ilmu.
- [7.] Elfiandri. (2018). *Komunikasi Lingkungan: Studi Literasi Kearifan lokal Masyarakat Adat Dalam Pelestarian Hutan Larangan (Imbo Laghangan)*. Depok: Rajawali Press.
- [8.] Hamacher, M. O. (1999). *Environmental Communication for Sustainable Development*. eter Lang GmbH, Internationaler Verlag der Wissenschaften.
- [9.] Herdiansyah, H. (2010). *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif Untuk Ilmu-Ilmu Sosial*. Jakarta: Salemba Humanika.
- [10.] Kadarisman, A. (2019). *Komunikasi Lingkungan: Pendekatan Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) dan Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)*. Bandung: Simbioasa Rekatama Media.
- [11.] Lidwina, I. A. (2015). PERILAKU PEDULI LINGKUNGAN DAN PENGEMBANGANNYA PADA ANAK USIA 5-6 TAHUN DI TK. *Jp Pendidikan*.
- [12.] Moleong, L. J. (2013). *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif Edisi Revisi*. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
- [13.] Morissan. (2019). *Riset Kualitatif*. Jakarta: Prenada Media Grup.
- [14.] Notoatmodjo, S. (2010). *Promosi Kesehatan dan Ilmu Perilaku*. Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta.
- [15.] Pendidikan, I. (2021, Februari 28). *Info Pendidikan*. From <https://infopendidikannews.com/2021/02/28/sman-7-bekasi-lakukan-penataan-dan-penghijauan-lingkungan/>
- [16.] Prof Dr Syukri Hamzah, M. (2013). *Pendidikan Lingkungan : sekelumit wawasan pengantar*. Bandung: 2013.
- [17.] Puspita, S. (2018, Agustus 19). *Kompas.com*. From <https://megapolitan.kompas.com/read/2018/08/19/21151811/indonesia-penyumbang-sampah-plastik-terbesar-kedua-di-dunia>
- [18.] Ruslan, R. (2003). *Manajemen Public Relations & Media Komunikasi Konsepsi dan Aplikasi*. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
- [19.] Sawitri, T. P. (2017). Hubungan Antara Sikap Dengan Perilaku Pro-Lingkungan Ditinjau dari. *Biology Education Conference* (pp. 214-217). Semarang: UNS.
- [20.] Sugiyono. (2007). *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif*. Bandung: CV ALfabeta.
- [21.] Suryabrata, S. (2004). *Metodologi Penelitian*. Jakarta : PT Grafindo.
- [22.] Subiakto, U.V, Peningkatan Kapasitas Pola Komunikasi Pengolahan Sampah Berbasis Karang Taruna di Wilayah Kembangan, Jakarta Barat, *Jurnal Abdi MOESTOPO Vol. 03, No. 02* (2020) *Jurnal Abdi MOESTOPO* ISSN: 2599-249X
- [23.] Uchjana, O. E. (2006). *Effendy, Onong Uchjana. Hubungan Masyarakat: Suatu Studi Komunikologis*. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
- [24.] Wijaya, Y. D. (2019, Desember 4). *Pena Belajar Kemendikbud*. <http://pena.belajar.kemdikbud.go.id/2019/12/mengembangkan-karakter-dengan-program-sekolah-adiwiyata/>
- [25.] Yenrizal. (2017). *Lestarian Bumi Dengan Komunikasi LInggungan*. Sleman: CV Budi Utama.
- [26.] Yin., R. K. (2011). *Studi Kasus: Desain & Metode*. Jakarta: PT Raja Grafindo Perkasa.
- [27.] Yoga Septian, M. R. (2016). PERILAKU RAMAH LINGKUNGAN PESERTA DIDIK . *Gea. Jurnal Pendidikan Geografi, Volume 16, Nomor 2, 71-81*.